

First record of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Kyrgyzstan

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae: Coreinae) in Kyrgyzstan is reported. The distribution of the species in Central Asia is summarised and discussed.

KEYWORDS: *Leptoglossus occidentalis*, invasive species, first record, distribution, Kyrgyzstan, Central Asia.

Leptoglossus occidentalis Heidemann, was observed and photographed on a balcony in the city of Cholpon-Ata (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae: Coreinae) is a Nearctic invasive species which has colonised nearly all parts of Europe (Aukema, 2024). In Central Asia, the species has been reported from Kazakhstan (Barclay & Nikolaeva, 2018) and Uzbekistan (van der Heyden, 2023), so far.

Now, the first record of *L. occidentalis* in Kyrgyzstan can be reported: On 03.09.2024, an adult specimen (Fig. 1)

photos were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Orlov, 2024).

Cholpon-Ata is located on the northern shore of Lake Issyk-Kul in the northern part of the country near the border with Kazakhstan. Likely, *L. occidentalis* arrived in Cholpon-Ata coming from the nearby region of Almaty in Kazakhstan where it

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was found several times (Barclay & Nikolaeva, 2018; iNaturalist, 2024).

The species might have entered Kyrgyzstan by human transport from the neighbouring country in the north.

I like to thank Mikhail Orlov for allowing me to use his photo of *L. occidentalis* to illustrate this note and for additional information about his finding.

Figure 1. Specimen of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910, Cholpon-Ata, Kyrgyzstan, 03.09.2024. (Photo: Mikhail Orlov).

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